

Determining and facilitating the clearest ways to visualize uncertainty around estimates, time series and curves

Migration charts

Employment charts

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Introduction

Uncertainty of many kinds is inherent in all measurements and can be important for decision-makers to take into account when considering such quantitative measures.

In this project we carried out an evaluation of different methods of visualisation of uncertainty around time series estimates and produced open-source software to enable these visualisations to be produced easily.

We worked closely with the Office of National Statistics and an expert user base for migration statistics (which included members of the civil service, journalists and think tank members).

National statistics are estimates and have considerable uncertainty about them – both quantified and unquantified. They also form the basis of many important decisions. It is therefore very important for users of these statistics (both expert and public) to appreciate the level of uncertainty around the estimates. In this study we investigated the representation of quantified uncertainties around two types of data – trends in UK net migration over time, and trends in UK unemployment over time – to investigate the generalisability of any results. The four types of uncertainty visualisation we tested are shown on the cover of this report.

The project had four main components:

- **A large quantitative study testing the comprehension of the lay public** of 4 different representations of uncertainty (compared with no uncertainty) with both migration and unemployment time series (see [p5](#)).
- **A small quantitative study of the comprehension of expert users** testing presentations of uncertainty versus no uncertainty on migration time series in order to determine differences between a lay and expert audience (see [p23](#)).
- **Qualitative interviews with a small group of expert users** of migration statistics ([p42](#)).
- **Development of Open Source software** to produce the different visualisations of uncertainty ([p59](#)).

Executive summary of findings

- Results for both the migration and unemployment data were in general very similar.
- Experts and the lay public were very similar in their preferences and comprehension.
- Presenting uncertainty in general did not affect peoples' objective comprehension.
- Presenting uncertainty in general did not affect peoples' perceptions of the reliability and trustworthiness of this data and its producers.
- Presenting uncertainty helped people assess the certainty of trends and may help them assess upper and lower likely limits to estimates.
- Expert users felt that the presentations of uncertainty were helpful to them in their everyday work and that they felt able to use them directly in reports to others.
- The 4 different presentations of uncertainty had very few significant effects on comprehension, and on perceptions of reliability, accuracy, trustworthiness and uncertainty. Where significant effects were detected, the size of the effects were very small but marginally in favour of the error bar or fuzzy fan as a representation of uncertainty.
- The charts with uncertainty (especially the fan chart and fuzzy chart) were rated subjectively as more difficult to understand than the chart with no uncertainty.
- None of the types of uncertainty presentation helped lay people realise that numbers closer to the midline of the distribution were more likely than those on the outside.
- For both the migration and unemployment data, participants' more positive feelings towards the state of the UK or about immigration were linked to their more positive perceptions of the accuracy, reliability and trustworthiness of the graphs they viewed and their producers, although effect sizes were small.

Example quotes from the qualitative interviews with expert users of migration statistics:

- *“This type of chart with uncertainty ranges helps illustrate that estimates are just that - indications of approximate scale, and not absolute values.”*
- *“I really like it, it’s a visual reminder of the uncertainty of the figures involved”*
- *“I think there would be some variation across readers, but those who take the time to look at it will come to a more informed conclusion.”*
- *“It may be harder for others to understand but it is more honest and that is what matters”*

With the caveats:

- *“My residual concern is that, by itself, the visual representation of statistical uncertainty in the charts could promote false confidence in the migration estimates, because this is not the only kind of uncertainty surrounding them. To be clear: I don't think this is a reason not to show the statistical uncertainty, but I think the other types of uncertainty affecting the data must also somehow be communicated to the user.”*
- *“The whole story isn’t being given in the data, it ignores all the things that aren’t measured. So one issue is how these things are being counted and also how they are assigned a level of usefulness that might not be reflected in reality.”*

Open Source software to create the charts

Our library of python scripts to create the visualisations of uncertainty is distributed via GitHub using pip. The github readme file describes installation and usage in detail.

GitHub: <https://github.com/WintonCentre/python-fuzzy-plots>

Our library is designed to work with the Jupyter notebook workflow, and we demonstrate a typical example of what data scientist might do with the library including data cleaning of and different plotting and customization using UK unemployment data provided by Office for National Statistics: https://nbviewer.jupyter.org/github/WintonCentre/python-fuzzy-plots/blob/master/examples/unemployment_example.ipynb

Large-scale quantitative study on lay understanding of uncertainty representations around migration and unemployment time series

Methodology

We designed four different graphical formats for presenting uncertainty around trends in UK net migration and compared them against a presentation of net migration without any uncertainty. The graphical formats are shown on the cover of this report, and will be referred to as ‘error bar chart’ (95% confidence interval shown in a pale colour around the central line), ‘fan chart’ (30%, 60% and 95% CIs shown as three bands of decreasing colour saturation outwards from the central estimate), ‘fuzzy fan chart’ (as above but with the boundaries between the bands blurred to look less distinct), and ‘fuzzy chart’ (full probability distribution as a colour density plot, with increased saturation of colour representing increased likelihood of the true value falling in that region).

Using the online platforms Qualtrics and Prolific, we tested the effects of our five treatments in a sample of UK participants. Each person only saw one of the 5 possible charts and were then asked questions about it. These questions tested their understanding of the chart and data, alongside their perceptions of how uncertain it was and how easy it was to understand; their feelings of trust and sense of accuracy and reliability of the data and of the producers of the data; their demographics, numeracy and political beliefs.

Sample characteristics - migration

The effects of the five treatments were tested on a sample of 1003 UK participants. Participants were aged between 18 and 74, with a mean age of 35.93 (sd 12.19). Participant gender was biased towards female, with 62.3% of participants identifying as female, 37.2% as male and 0.4% as other. Participants showed a good distribution across types of educational qualification, with 16.2% at GCSE level or equivalent, 23.9% at A-level or equivalent, 12.3% with other higher education qualifications, 33.0% with bachelor’s degrees, 12.9% with masters degrees and 0.9% with doctoral degrees, whilst 0.6% of participants said they had no qualification. There was also a fairly even distribution of participants across self-reported political views, although with some skew towards a liberal outlook.

Sample characteristics - unemployment

The effects of the five treatments were tested on a sample of 1000 UK participants. Participants were aged between 18 and 81, with a mean age of 37.08 (sd 12.99). Participant gender was biased towards female, with 65.2% of participants identifying as female, 34.1% as male and 0.5% as other. Participants showed a good distribution across types of educational qualification, with 16.6% at GCSE level or equivalent, 22.0% at A-level or equivalent, 9.4% with other higher education qualifications, 34.2% with bachelor’s degrees, 13.6% with masters degrees and 2.5% with doctoral degrees, whilst 1.2% of participants said they had no qualification. There was also a fairly even distribution of participants across self-reported political views, although with some skew towards a liberal outlook.

Comprehension – analyses and summary

Comprehension questions were designed to assess participants' understanding of the information depicted in the graphs and whether this differed between the different graphical formats tested. It should be noted that although some differences between treatments were detected for both the migration and the unemployment data, these effects were small and will likely have low "real world" impact. Results were broadly similar for the migration and unemployment data.

Participant numeracy had no moderating influence on the relationship between condition and any of the comprehension variables in either dataset. There were some small, direct effects of numeracy on certain measures of comprehension. For example, participants with higher numeracy perceived the different graphs to be easier to interpret. There was also a relationship between numeracy and estimates of upper bounds for net migration and unemployment taken from the graph, and confidence in these estimates (confidence in upper and lower bounds for unemployment, confidence in lower bound only for migration). Again, effects sizes were small.

Q. Self-reported degree to which participants found the graphs easy to understand: measured on a 7-point scale from "Very difficult" to "Very easy"

Migration

Results demonstrated that the Fan chart and the Fuzzy chart were significantly less easy to understand than the Control chart (where no uncertainty was presented). Ease of understanding for the other uncertainty treatments (Error bar chart and Fuzzy-Fan chart) did not differ significantly from the Control treatment, nor from any other uncertainty treatment.

(NB scale is reflected and sqrt transformed so **smaller values imply easier comprehension**)

Unemployment

Results demonstrated that all uncertainty conditions were significantly less easy to understand than the Control chart (where no uncertainty was presented). Ease of understanding did not differ significantly between the different uncertainty treatments.

(NB scale is reflected and sqrt transformed so **smaller values imply easier comprehension**)

Q. Participants were asked how true they thought the statement “The graph shows that more people came to the UK than left”. This was measured on a 7-point scale from “Not at all true” to “Completely true” (Migration only)

Migration

Results showed that comprehension was fairly poor across all treatments, with more participants answering incorrectly than correctly. The relationship between understanding of net migration and the specific treatment a participant was in bordered on significance, with comprehension slightly worse in the Fan chart condition. Given the fact that this effect was small and only marginally significant however, it should not be given much weight. There were no other differences between treatments for how well participants comprehended the concept of net migration.

No employment equivalent.

Q. Participants were asked to choose an answer to the question:

“Was net migration higher in March 2018 than it was in March 2017?” (Migration)

“Was unemployment lower in October 2018 than it was in October 2017?” (Unemployment)

Answers were on a categorical scale and options included:

- a. Yes, definitely
- b. Yes, probably
- c. It was about the same
- d. No, probably not
- e. No, definitely not
- f. Can't tell
- g. Don't know

In addition to being a measure of comprehension, this question was also designed to give some indication as to whether participants in conditions where uncertainty was presented acknowledged this uncertainty more in their answers than participants in the control condition where no uncertainty was presented.

Migration

For the migration data, the correct answer would be ‘yes’, and the majority of participants across all conditions chose one of the two yes options (“Yes, definitely” or “Yes, probably”), suggesting that they were able to correctly comprehend the trend being asked about.

Analyses demonstrated that there was a significant difference between treatments in the answers that participants chose, with participants in the Control condition acknowledging uncertainty less than in the Error bar condition. There were no clear differences amongst other treatments in terms of acknowledgement of uncertainty.

Was net migration higher in March 2018 than it was in March 2017? * Condition Crosstabulation

Count		Condition					Total
		Control	Error Bar	Fan	Fuzzy	Fuzzy Fan	
Was net migration higher in March 2018 than it was in March 2017?	Yes, definitely	138	104	124	120	123	609
	Yes, probably	32	71	58	56	52	269
	It was about the same	6	3	1	2	2	14
	No, probably not	8	7	4	9	8	36
	No, definitely not	15	12	7	8	13	55
	Can't tell	2	4	6	3	2	17
	Don't know	0	1	0	1	1	3
Total		201	202	200	199	201	1003

Unemployment

For the unemployment data, the trend being asked about is far less clear. Answers of “Yes, probably” and “It was about the same” are both viable options. Across all conditions, the most popular answer amongst participants was the option “It was about the same”, followed by “Yes, probably”, suggesting that they were able to correctly comprehend the trend being asked about.

Analyses demonstrated that there was a marginally significant difference between treatments in the answers that participants chose, with participants in the Control condition acknowledging uncertainty less than in the Fuzzy Fan condition. Participants in the Control condition were significantly more likely to choose the option “Yes definitely” than expected by chance, and significantly less likely to choose the option “It was about the same”. Participants in the Fuzzy-Fan condition were significantly more likely to choose the option “It was about the same” than expected by chance. Participants in the Fan condition were less likely to choose the option “Yes, probably” than expected by chance. Counts indicate that instead they were more likely to choose the option “It was about the same”, however this particular post-hoc comparison was not significant so a concrete conclusion cannot be drawn for the Fan chart. There were no clear differences amongst other treatments in terms of acknowledgement of uncertainty.

Was unemployment lower in October 2018 than it was in October 2017? * Condition Crosstabulation

Count		Condition					Total
		Control	Error Bar	Fan	Fuzzy	Fuzzy Fan	
Was unemployment lower in October 2018 than it was in October 2017?	Yes, definitely	26	18	10	14	14	82
	Yes, probably	36	38	21	35	25	155
	It was about the same	114	118	138	125	142	637
	No, probably not	14	12	16	13	7	62
	No, definitely not	12	9	11	10	8	50
	Can't tell	0	4	4	3	1	12
	Don't know	0	1	0	0	0	1
Total		202	200	200	200	197	999

Q. Since October 2014, has unemployment gone up or down? (Unemployment only)

This question was given to participants in the employment study as another measure of comprehension and acknowledgement of uncertainty, measured on a 7-point scale from “Up a lot” to “Down a lot”. The trend in question is quite strongly downwards, so the correct answer would be “Down” or “Down a lot”.

Across all conditions, the majority of participants chose the option “Down” followed by the option “Down a lot”. There were no significant differences between treatments in

participant choice, indicating that comprehension was consistent across treatments and acknowledgement of uncertainty did not differ between treatments, regardless of whether uncertainty was presented around the central trend or not.

Since October 2014, has unemployment gone up or down? * Condition Crosstabulation

Count

		Condition					Total
		Control	Error Bar	Fan	Fuzzy	Fuzzy Fan	
Since October 2014, has unemployment gone up or down?	Up a lot	1	0	0	0	0	1
	Up	0	0	0	1	2	3
	Up a bit	4	3	4	1	4	16
	Neither up nor down	0	0	0	1	2	3
	Down a bit	22	25	28	23	21	119
	Down	139	142	126	143	134	684
	Down a lot	36	30	42	31	34	173
Total		202	200	200	200	197	999

Q. Since October 2016, has unemployment gone up or down? (Unemployment only)

This question was given to participants in the employment study as another measure of comprehension and acknowledgement of uncertainty, measured on a 7-point scale from “Up a lot” to “Down a lot”. The trend in question was less definitively downwards than the previous question, so the correct answer would be “Down” or “Down a bit”.

Across all conditions, the majority of participants chose the option “Down a bit” followed by the option “Down”. There were no significant differences between treatments in participant choice, indicating that comprehension was consistent across treatments and acknowledgement of uncertainty did not differ between treatments, regardless of whether uncertainty was presented around the central trend or not. The fact that “Down a bit” was the most popular option (as compared to the option “Down” for the more definitive trend asked about in the previous question) is another indication of good comprehension across treatments.

Since October 2016, has unemployment gone up or down? * Condition Crosstabulation

Count

		Condition					Total
		Control	Error Bar	Fan	Fuzzy	Fuzzy Fan	
Since October 2016, has unemployment gone up or down?	Up a lot	1	0	0	0	0	1
	Up	0	0	0	0	1	1
	Up a bit	4	5	3	3	4	19
	Neither up nor down	9	9	8	9	10	45
	Down a bit	116	127	130	131	117	621
	Down	63	58	57	53	58	289
	Down a lot	9	1	2	4	7	23
Total		202	200	200	200	197	999

Q: Participants were asked:

“What does the graph show net migration was in March 2015? Please write your answer as a number below:”. Data were a continuous series of free-entry estimates inputted by participants. (Migration)

“How many unemployed people were there in October 2017?” Data were a continuous series of estimates made using a slider scaled from zero to two million. (Unemployment)

NB: To remove extreme outliers, the migration data were subsetting between 100,000 and 400,000, and the employment data were subsetting between 1,000,000 and 2,600,000. Both datasets remained skewed so non-parametric Kruskal Wallis tests were used in analysis.

Migration

For the migration data, estimates were lower in the Error Bar condition than in the Fuzzy and Fuzzy-Fan conditions, although when adjusted for multiple comparisons these differences became non-significant.

Unemployment

For the unemployment data, there was no difference between conditions in the size of the estimates.

Q. Participants were asked to estimate a plausible upper bound for net migration in March 2016, and unemployment in October 2016, via the question “Looking at the estimate for March 2016/October 2016, how high do you think the actual number for net migration/unemployment might be?”. The same question was asked for a lower bound for the estimate.

For migration, data were a continuous series of free-entry estimates inputted by participants. For unemployment, data were a continuous series of estimates made using a slider scaled from zero to two million.

NB: To remove extreme outliers, the migration data were subsetting between 100,000 and 400,000, and the employment data were subsetting between 1,000,000 and 2,600,000. Both datasets remained skewed thus non-parametric Kruskal Wallis tests were used in analysis.

Migration

For the upper bound estimate for migration, estimates were lower in the Control condition than in all other conditions where uncertainty was presented. This indicates that where uncertainty is *not* presented around the trend in net migration, participants may be anchoring more to the central trend line (i.e. their estimates may be more influenced by that central trend line) than when uncertainty *is* presented. Post hoc comparisons also reveal that the upper bound estimates were significantly lower in the fuzzy and in the fan condition as compared to the error bar condition, however these contrasts did not remain significant after adjustment for multiple comparisons.

It is difficult to draw concrete conclusions about such anchoring effects however. Indeed, when participants were asked to estimate a *lower* bound for net migration in March 2016, although these estimates were higher in the Control condition than in the Error Bar and the Fan Chart condition (consistent with the anchoring effect described previously), after adjustment for multiple comparisons there were no significant differences between the

magnitude of estimates in the Control condition and the Fuzzy and Fuzzy-Fan conditions. In turn, lower bound estimates for the Fuzzy and the Fuzzy-Fan conditions were also significantly higher than for the Error Bar and the Fan chart conditions (although not than the Control condition). Thus if there is any anchoring effect in conditions where uncertainty is not presented, this effect will likely be small, and is not definitive.

Unemployment

For the unemployment data, there were no significant differences amongst any of the treatments nor the control in the estimates given for the upper and lower bounds. This reinforces the idea that any anchoring effect is subtle (although it should also be noted that the uncertainty bands in the employment data are narrower than in the migration data so might be expected to have less of an effect on upper and lower bound estimations).

Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test

Total N	797
Test Statistic	1.010
Degrees of Freedom	4
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.908

1. The test statistic is adjusted for ties.
2. Multiple comparisons are not performed because the overall test does not show significant differences across samples.

Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test

Total N	786
Test Statistic	9.153
Degrees of Freedom	4
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.057

1. The test statistic is adjusted for ties.
2. Multiple comparisons are not performed because the overall test does not show significant differences across samples.

Q: Participants were asked how confident they were about their estimate of both the upper and lower bounds for net migration and unemployment, discussed above. This was measured on a continuous 7-point scale from “Not confident at all” to “Very confident”.

Migration

When estimating an upper bound, there was no difference between treatments in participants’ confidence i.e. presentation of uncertainty does not change confidence in inferences about upper and lower bounds made from the graphs.

Confidence in Upper bound estimate (NB scale is reflected and sqrt transformed so **smaller values imply higher confidence**)

Interestingly, these trends were more stark for participants’ confidence in their estimate of a lower bound for net migration. Indeed, participants in the Control condition were significantly *less* confident about their estimate than in all other conditions, suggesting that the presentation of uncertainty may increase confidence in estimates relating to upper and lower bounds.

Confidence in Lower bound estimate (NB scale is reflected and sqrt transformed so **smaller values imply higher confidence**)

Employment

For employment data, there was no significant difference amongst treatments in participants' confidence in their upper and lower bound estimates.

Q: Participants were asked:

“How much would you say net migration has varied (gone up and down) over the timeline shown in the graph?” (Migration)

“Over the timeline shown in the graph, how much has the number of unemployed people varied (gone up and down) between months?” (Employment)

Both were measured on a continuous 7-point scale from “Not at all” to “A lot”

Migration

It was expected that perceptions of this variation over time would be lower in those conditions where uncertainty was presented than in the Control condition with no uncertainty, however analyses of the migration data revealed no significant differences between treatments in perceptions of variation across the time series.

Unemployment

The same results were obtained for the employment data.

Q: Participants were asked the question:

“The graph shows that between March 2014 and March 2015, net migration went:...”
(Migration)

The graph shows that between October 2016 and October 2017, unemployment went:”
(Unemployment)

Measured on a continuous 7-point scale from “Up a lot” to “Down a lot”.

This question was again intended to measure comprehension, but also in part to assess participant acknowledgement of uncertainty in their answer; although the trend in question was quite strongly upwards for migration, and fairly strongly downwards for unemployment, we were interested to assess whether participants would rate this trend as less strong in those conditions where uncertainty was presented versus in the control condition.

Migration

For migration, results demonstrated that, in terms of comprehension, the majority of participants across all treatments were able to correctly understand the direction of the trend in question (up). There was no difference between treatments however, in the strength that participants allocated to this trend i.e. in this instance, participants did not appear to be more acknowledging of uncertainty in those conditions where it was explicitly presented versus where it was not presented at all.

Unemployment

For unemployment, results were similar - the majority of participants across all treatments correctly comprehended the direction of the trend in question (down a bit). There was no difference between treatments.

Q: Finally, participants in those conditions where uncertainty was presented were tested on their comprehension of the distribution of possible values for net migration/unemployment across the uncertainty range displayed.

Migration

Across all conditions, almost half of participants comprehended the concept of this range correctly, choosing the answer that described the distribution of possible values around the central trend line: “Values closer towards the middle of the range are more likely than values at both ends of the range”. The next most popular answer across all treatments (and thus the most popular misconception) was “All values between the minimum and maximum are equally likely”.

There were no significant differences between the different presentations of uncertainty in terms of the answers that people gave i.e. the particular presentation of uncertainty around the trend in net migration did not affect participants’ comprehension of the nature of the distribution of possible values for net migration.

Unemployment

Results were the same for the unemployment data.

Measures of Trustworthiness and Reliability – analyses and summary

Participants were asked:

- How strong would you say the evidence is that, since March 2016, net migration has gone down? (Migration only)
- How accurate do you think that the net migration/employment estimates depicted in the graph are?
- How reliable do you think the net migration/employment estimates depicted in the graph are?
- How trustworthy do you think the net migration/employment estimates depicted in the graph are?
- How trustworthy do you think the statisticians who are responsible for these net Migration/employment estimates are?
- How reliable do you think that government statistics in general are?
- To what extent do you think that the net migration/employment estimates depicted in the graph are certain or uncertain?
- How much uncertainty do you think there is about these net migration/employment estimates?

Migration

Analyses reveal no significant differences in participant perceptions between treatments in any cases.

Unemployment

Analyses reveal no significant differences in participant perceptions between treatments in any cases.

Participant numeracy had no moderating influence on the relationship between condition and any of the above variables in either dataset. There were some significant relationships between numeracy and certain variables however.

For migration, participants with higher numeracy perceived the net migration estimates depicted in the graphs to be more accurate, reliable and trustworthy, and also perceived them as being less uncertain.

For unemployment, this relationship was significant only for the relationship between numeracy and perceived accuracy.

For both the migration and the unemployment data, participants with higher numeracy perceived government statistics in general to be more reliable, statisticians to be more trustworthy.

Prior beliefs and perceptions of uncertainty, accuracy, reliability and trustworthiness – analyses and summary

Before being presented with any graph, all participants were asked questions regarding their beliefs about a variety of social issues, including both immigration and unemployment. Analyses revealed an important role for beliefs in predicting their perceptions of the uncertainty, accuracy, reliability and trustworthiness of the graphs they subsequently viewed, although effect sizes were small. Details of these analyses are given below.

Q. On the whole, how dissatisfied or satisfied are you with the way things are going in the United Kingdom today? (1-7 scale from 1 = Very dissatisfied to 7 = Very satisfied).

Regression analyses were used to assess the predictive power of this variable on our eight different measures of uncertainty, reliability, accuracy and trustworthiness.

Migration

Analyses revealed no relationship between participant satisfaction with how things were going in the UK and perceptions of the strength of evidence that since March 2016 net migration has gone down, nor with perceived accuracy of the trends depicted in the graph. Prior beliefs regarding satisfaction were predictive of participant perceptions of reliability and trustworthiness of the trends however; as satisfaction increased, participant perceptions of reliability and trustworthiness also increased. The same positive trend was observed for the relationship between satisfaction and perceived trustworthiness of statisticians, and between satisfaction and perceived reliability of government statistics in general. Greater satisfaction also related to perceptions of the depicted trends as being more certain.

Unemployment

Analyses revealed that participant satisfaction with how things are going in the UK predicted perceptions of the strength of evidence that since October 2017, unemployment has gone down; the more satisfied participants felt with the state of the UK, the stronger they rated the evidence for the downwards trend in unemployment. In turn, greater participant satisfaction also predicted higher ratings of the accuracy, reliability and trustworthiness of the trends depicted, and of the trustworthiness of statisticians and reliability of government statistics in general. Greater positivity also related to perceptions of the depicted trends as being more certain.

Q. Is the UK made a worse or a better place to live by people coming to live here from other countries? (1-7 scale from 1 = Worse place to live to 7 = Better place to live)

Regression analyses were used to assess the predictive power of this variable on our eight different measures of uncertainty, reliability, accuracy and trustworthiness.

Migration

Analyses revealed that participant positivity about the effects of immigrants on the UK predicted perceptions of the strength of evidence that since March 2016 net migration has gone down; the more positive participants felt about immigrants, the stronger they rated the evidence for the downwards trend in immigration. In turn, greater participant positivity about immigrants also predicted higher ratings of the accuracy, reliability and trustworthiness of the trends depicted, and of the trustworthiness of statisticians and reliability of government statistics in general. Greater positivity also related to perceptions of the depicted trends as being more certain.

Unemployment

Despite being specific to immigration, participant perceptions of the effects of immigrants on the UK also predicted several variables relating to unemployment. More specifically, the more positive participants felt about the effects of immigrants, the more reliable and trustworthy they perceived the unemployment graphs to be, the more trustworthy they perceived statisticians to be, and the more reliable they perceived government statistics in general to be. Participants with more positive views of immigrants also perceived less uncertainty around the employment estimates depicted. In contrast to the migration data, participants who held more positive attitudes towards immigrants perceived the evidence for the downwards trend in unemployment since October 2017 to be less strong than those with negative attitudes. These attitudes did not relate to perceptions of accuracy of the unemployment estimates.

Q. What do you think overall about the state of unemployment in the United Kingdom at the moment? (1-7 scale from 1 = Very bad, a lot of unemployment to 7 = Very good, little unemployment)

Migration

Despite being specific to unemployment, participant perceptions of the state of unemployment in the UK also predicted several variables relating to migration. More specifically, the more positive participants felt about the state of unemployment, the more accurate, reliable and trustworthy they perceived the migration graphs to be, the more trustworthy they perceived statisticians to be, and the more reliable they perceived government statistics in general to be. Participants with more positive views also rated the evidence for the downwards trend in migration since 2016 as stronger than those with more

negative views. Participant views on the state of unemployment did not relate to how much uncertainty they perceived around the migration trends depicted.

Unemployment

Analyses revealed that greater satisfaction with the state of unemployment in the UK predicted higher ratings of the accuracy, reliability and trustworthiness of the trends depicted, and of the trustworthiness of statisticians and reliability of government statistics in general. Greater positivity also related to perceptions of the depicted trends as being more certain. There was no relationship between satisfaction about the state of unemployment and participants perceptions about the strength of evidence for a downwards trend in unemployment since October 2017.

Small quantitative study on the understanding of uncertainty representations around migration time series by expert users

Background

The aim of this study was to explore the effects of communicating uncertainty around trends in migration statistics on expert users of the Migration Statistics Quarterly Report (MSQR). Because we anticipated a small sample size we particularly investigated their responses to the "Fuzzy-fan chart". The first section of the study presented participants with only one graph (randomly either the fuzzy fan or the graph with no uncertainty) and tested participant comprehension and perceptions of reliability, accuracy, uncertainty and trustworthiness. The second section of the experiment showed participants both the fuzzy-fan and control treatment graphs together, in addition to the fan chart version of the graph. After viewing these three graphs, participants were asked a variety of questions regarding how useful they would find each for performing their day to day job.

Participants

Twenty-two expert users of the MSQR participated in this study. Participants were aged between 24 and 60, with a mean age of 37.86 (standard deviation: 11.06). Eight participants (36.4%) identified as female and 14 (63.6%) as male. These users represented a variety of sectors, including government/civil service (68.2%), journalists/bloggers (9.1%), think tanks (9.1%) and academics (9.1%). While all would be rated as expert users as compared to a public audience, they had a diversity of expertise with the MSQR and statistics in general.

Table 1: The frequency with which experts use the MSQR.

Frequency of use	Number of people (Total N = 22)
Daily	5
Weekly	5
Monthly	10
Quarterly	2

Table 2 The employment sector the experts represented.

Employment sector	Number of people (Total N = 22)
Civil service/government	15
Journalist/blogger	2
Think tank	2
Academic	2
Other	1

Table 3: Experts' self-reported expertise with migration statistics.

Expertise with migration statistics	Number of people (Total N = 22)
Highly expert user	3
Expert user	11
Average user	7
Other	1

Comprehension

Due to the small sample size and distribution issues, the data were analysed descriptively, using Hedges' g as a measure of effect size of analyses involving continuous response variables. Hedges' g was used rather than Cohen's d due to there being different sample sizes between the two treatment groups. Effect sizes should be considered alongside their associated confidence intervals – even where an effect size is large, a large confidence interval, particularly one that encompasses zero, indicates considerable uncertainty about the reliability of the effect in question.

Q1 How easy or difficult do you find this graph to understand? (7-point scale from Very difficult to Very easy)

This variable measures participants' self-reported ease of understanding of the chart they viewed. Using Hedges' g as a measure of effect size indicated a small effect of uncertainty treatment on ease of understanding (-0.162 , 95% CI upper bound = 0.733 , 95% CI lower bound = -1.06). Estimates in the fuzzy-fan condition ($M=6.10$, $SD = 1.29$) were slightly larger than in the control condition ($M = 5.92$, $SD = 0.900$). Note that confidence intervals around this small effect size encompass zero.

This indicates that there is a negligible effect of the presentation of uncertainty on participants' ease of understanding.

Q2 Was net migration higher in March 2018 than it was in March 2017?

Answer options:

Yes, definitely

Yes, probably
It was about the same
No, probably not
No, definitely not
Can't tell

This is a categorical variable measuring participants' comprehension of the graph and giving an indication of their perceptions of uncertainty. In terms of comprehension, it is difficult to say definitively what the "correct" answer is. If you're in the control condition then based on the graph alone, the answer would be "Yes, definitely" (although participants may be taking into account uncertainty in their answer, regardless of whether they've seen it or not, so may instead choose "Yes, probably" or even some other option). In the fuzzy-fan condition, the "most correct" answer is likely to be "Yes probably" i.e. acknowledging uncertainty. Generally then, we could label both "Yes, definitely" and "Yes probably" as being "correct" answers in terms of comprehension. On this basis, the majority of participants in both treatments got the answer to this question correct.

In terms of the effects of treatment on perceptions of uncertainty, the small sample size and resultant low number of counts per cell mean that making concrete inferences is difficult. Adjusted standardised residuals indicate that more people in the control condition may be choosing the option "Yes, definitely" than in the fuzzy-fan uncertainty condition, where choices are distributed across some of the more uncertain options (e.g. "Yes, probably").

This result indicates greater acknowledgement of uncertainty in the fuzzy-fan condition versus the control condition, however the small sample size means this result should not be relied upon.

NB We cannot use a Chi square test to examine for significant differences between actual and expected counts for each option as some expected counts are fewer than five.

Condition * Based on the evidence in the graph, was net migration higher in March 2018 than it was in March 2017? Crosstabulation

		Based on the evidence in the graph, was net migration higher in March 2018 than it was in March 2017?					
		Yes, definitely	Yes, probably	It was about the same	Can't tell	Total	
Condition	Control	Count	7	5	0	0	12
		Expected Count	4.4	6.0	1.1	.5	12.0
		% within Condition	58.3%	41.7%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		Adjusted Residual	2.3	-.9	-1.6	-1.1	
	Fuzzy Fan	Count	1	6	2	1	10
		Expected Count	3.6	5.0	.9	.5	10.0
		% within Condition	10.0%	60.0%	20.0%	10.0%	100.0%
		Adjusted Residual	-2.3	.9	1.6	1.1	
Total	Count	8	11	2	1	22	
	Expected Count	8.0	11.0	2.0	1.0	22.0	
	% within Condition	36.4%	50.0%	9.1%	4.5%	100.0%	

Based on the evidence in the graph, was net migration higher in March 2018 than it was in March 2017?

Error bars: 95% CI

Q3 Looking at the estimate for March 2016, how high do you think the actual number for net migration might be?

Data were a continuous series of estimates made using a slider scaled from zero to 400,000. Using Hedges' g as a measure of effect size indicated a large effect of the fuzzy-fan uncertainty treatment on estimates of an upper bound for net migration (-1.15, 95% CI upper bound = -0.11, 95% CI lower bound = -2.20). Estimates in the fuzzy-fan condition ($M = 350099.89$, $SD = 19406.77$) were larger than in the Control condition ($M = 314030.60$, $SD = 36772.31$).

This indicates that there is an effect of the presentation of uncertainty on participants' upper bound estimate. Note that this effect is not necessarily indicative of a significant difference – sample size and distribution restrictions meant inferential statistical analysis was not possible.

Q4 How confident are you about your answer to the previous question? (1-7 scale that runs from Not confident at all – Very confident)

Using Hedges' g as a measure of effect size indicated a small effect of the fuzzy fan uncertainty treatment on participant ratings of confidence (-0.393, 95% CI upper bound = 0.586, 95% CI lower bound = -1.372). Ratings of confidence were slightly higher in the fuzzy-fan condition ($M = 5.10$, $SD = 1.66$) than in the control condition ($M = 4.44$, $SD = 1.51$). Note that confidence intervals around this small effect size encompass zero.

This indicates that there is a negligible effect of the presentation of uncertainty on participants' confidence in their upper bound estimate.

Q5 Looking at the estimate for March 2016, how low do you think the actual number for net migration might be?

Data were a continuous series of estimates made using a slider scaled from zero to 400,000. Using Hedges' g as a measure of effect size indicated a small effect of the fuzzy-fan uncertainty treatment on estimates of a lower bound for net migration (-0.096 , 95% CI upper bound = 0.819 , 95% CI lower bound = -1.011). Estimates in the fuzzy-fan condition ($M = 297159.30$, $SD = 14719.66$) were slightly larger than in the Control condition ($M = 293325.91$, $SD = 50803.84$). Note that confidence intervals around this small effect size encompass zero.

This indicates that there is a negligible effect of the presentation of uncertainty on participants' lower bound estimate.

Q6 How confident are you about your answer to the previous question? (1-7 scale that runs from Not confident at all – Very confident)

Using Hedges' *g* as a measure of effect size indicated a small effect of the fuzzy fan uncertainty treatment on participant ratings of confidence (-0.229, 95% CI upper bound = 0.667, 95% CI lower bound = -1.125). Ratings of confidence were slightly higher in the fuzzy-fan condition (M = 5.10, SD = 1.66) than in the control condition (M = 4.75, SD = 1.29). Note that confidence intervals around this small effect size encompass zero.

This indicates that there is a negligible effect of the presentation of uncertainty on participants' confidence in their lower bound estimate.

Q7 How much would you say net migration has varied (gone up and down) over the timeline shown in the graph? (1-7 scale from “Not at all” to “A lot”)

Using Hedges’ g as a measure of effect size indicated a small effect of the fuzzy fan uncertainty treatment on participant perceptions of variability in the migration trend (-0.215 , 95% CI upper bound = 0.681 , 95% CI lower bound = -1.11). Ratings of variability were slightly higher in the fuzzy-fan condition ($M = 5.50$, $SD = 0.707$) than in the control condition ($M = 5.33$, $SD = 0.778$). Note that confidence intervals around this small effect size encompass zero.

This indicates that there is a negligible effect of the presentation of uncertainty on participants’ perceptions of variability.

Uncertainty, reliability and trustworthiness – analyses.

Due to the small sample size and distribution issues, the data were analysed descriptively, using Hedges' g as a measure of effect size of analyses involving continuous response variables. Hedges' g was used rather than Cohen's d due to there being different sample sizes between the two treatment groups. Effect sizes should be considered alongside their associated confidence intervals – even where an effect size is large, a large confidence interval, particularly one that encompasses zero, indicates considerable uncertainty about the reliability of the effect in question.

Q1 How strong would you say the evidence is that, since March 2017, net migration has gone up? (Scale from 1-7 where 1 = Not strong at all and 7 = Very strong)

Using Hedges' g as a measure of effect size indicated a large effect of the fuzzy fan uncertainty treatment on participant perceptions of strength of evidence (0.858, 95% CI upper bound = 1.79, 95% CI lower bound = -0.075). Ratings of strength of evidence were lower in the fuzzy-fan condition (M = 3.60, SD = 1.71) than in the control condition (M = 5.08, SD = 1.62).

This indicates that presenting uncertainty results in participants perceiving the strength of evidence of a trend to be lower than where no uncertainty is presented (i.e. more uncertainty is perceived), although note that confidence intervals around this effect size encompass zero.

Q2 How accurate do you think that the net migration estimates depicted in the graph are? (Scale from 1 to 10 where 1 = Not accurate at all and 10 = Extremely accurate).

Using Hedges' g as a measure of effect size indicated a small effect of the fuzzy-fan treatment on participant perceptions of accuracy (0.080, 95% CI upper bound = 0.973, 95% CI lower bound = -0.814). Ratings of accuracy were slightly lower in the fuzzy fan condition ($M = 5.90$, $SD = 2.51$) than in the control condition ($M = 6.08$, $SD = 1.93$). Note that confidence intervals around this small effect size encompass zero.

This indicates that there is a negligible effect of the presentation of uncertainty on participants' perceptions of accuracy.

Q3 How reliable do you think the net migration estimates depicted in the graph are? (7-point scale from 1 = Not reliable at all to 7 = Very reliable)

Using Hedges' g as a measure of effect size indicated a small effect of the fuzzy-fan treatment on participant perceptions of reliability (-0.145, 95% CI upper bound = 0.750, 95% CI lower bound = -1.04). Ratings of reliability were slightly higher in the fuzzy fan condition ($M = 4.40$, $SD = 1.71$) than in the control condition ($M = 4.17$, $SD = 1.40$). Note that confidence intervals around this small effect size encompass zero.

This indicates that there is a negligible effect of the presentation of uncertainty on participants' perceptions of reliability.

Q4 How trustworthy do you think the net migration estimates depicted in the graph are? (7-point scale from Not trustworthy at all to Very trustworthy)

Using Hedges' g as a measure of effect size indicated a small effect of the fuzzy-fan treatment on participant perceptions of trustworthiness (-0.310 , 95% CI upper bound = 0.588 , 95% CI lower bound = -1.21). Ratings of trustworthiness were slightly higher in the fuzzy fan condition ($M = 4.60$, $SD = 1.71$) than in the control condition ($M = 4.08$, $SD = 1.51$). Note that confidence intervals around this small effect size encompass zero.

This indicates that there is a negligible effect of the presentation of uncertainty on participants' perceptions of trustworthiness.

Q5 To what extent do you think that the net migration estimates depicted in the graph are certain or uncertain?

Using Hedges' g as a measure of effect size indicated a small effect of the fuzzy-fan treatment on participant perceptions of uncertainty (0.112, 95% CI upper bound = 1.01, 95% CI lower bound = -0.782). Ratings of uncertainty were (counter to expectations) slightly lower in the fuzzy fan condition ($M = 4.40$, $SD = 1.84$) than in the control condition ($M = 4.58$, $SD = 1.31$). Note that confidence intervals around this small effect size encompass zero.

This indicates that there is a negligible effect of the presentation of uncertainty on participants' perceptions of uncertainty.

Estimated Marginal Means of To what extent do you think that the net migration estimates depicted in the graph are certain or uncertain?

Within-subjects comparison between treatments

To account for temporal pseudoreplication due to repeated sampling of participants, analyses to determine the differences between the effects of the two uncertainty treatments and the control on participant perceptions would ideally use a mixed effects modelling approach. Sample size restrictions and distributional issues however, limit the robustness and reliability of these models in providing inference. Thus effect size calculations using a simple Cohen's d approach will be used to provide descriptive detail of the differences between the different treatments. Note that these effect sizes are not adjusted for the non-independence of errors and nor do they provide information on the significance of differences. Effect sizes should be considered alongside their associated confidence intervals – even where an effect size is large, a large confidence interval, particularly one that encompasses zero, indicates considerable uncertainty about the reliability of the effect in question.

Q1: How easy or difficult do you find Graph A (Control)/B (Fuzzy-Fan)/C (Fan) to understand? (7-point scale from 1 (Very difficult) to 7 (Very easy))

Using Cohen's d as a measure of effect size indicated a medium effect of the fuzzy fan uncertainty treatment on participant perceptions of ease of interpretation as compared to the control (0.564, 95% CI upper bound = 1.18, 95% CI lower bound = -0.0564). The fuzzy fan condition was rated less easy to understand ($M = 5.57$, $SD = 1.36$) than the control condition ($M = 6.24$, $SD = 0.831$).

This indicates that presenting uncertainty in the format of a fuzzy-fan chart makes the chart less easy to understand than when no uncertainty is presented, although it should be noted that confidence intervals around this effect size encompass zero.

Similarly, Cohen's d indicated a medium effect of the fan chart uncertainty treatment on participant perceptions of ease of interpretation as compared to the control (0.544, 95% CI upper bound = 1.17, 95% CI lower bound = -0.0831). The fan chart was rated less easy to understand ($M = 5.52$, $SD = 1.78$) than the control treatment ($M = 6.24$, $SD = 0.831$).

This indicates that presenting uncertainty in the format of a fan chart makes the chart less easy to understand than when no uncertainty is presented, although it should be noted that confidence intervals around this effect size again encompass zero.

There was a small effect size for the difference between the fuzzy-fan and fan chart presentations in terms of participant's ratings of how easy they were to understand (-0.0712, 95% CI upper bound = 0.545, 95% CI lower bound = -0.688). The fuzzy-fan chart ($M = 5.57$, $SD = 1.36$) was rated very slightly easier to understand than the fan chart ($M = 5.52$, $SD = 1.78$). Again, confidence intervals around the small effect size encompassed zero.

This indicates that presenting uncertainty in the format of a fuzzy-fan chart has a negligible effect on ease of understanding as compared to using a fan chart.

Q2 How useful would you find Graph A (Control)/B (Fuzzy-Fan)/C (Fan) in informing the work that you do? (7-point scale from 1 (Extremely useful) to 7 (Not useful at all))

Cohen's *d* indicated a medium effect of the fuzzy fan uncertainty treatment on participant perceptions of the usefulness of the graph in informing their work as compared to the control (0.626, 95% CI upper bound = 1.25, 95% CI lower bound = 0.003). The fuzzy fan condition was rated more useful ($M = 2.71$, $SD = 1.77$) than the control condition ($M = 3.67$, $SD = 1.74$).

This indicates that presenting uncertainty in the format of a fuzzy-fan chart makes the chart more useful for experts in their day to day job than when no uncertainty is presented.

Cohen's *d* indicated a small effect of the fan chart uncertainty treatment on participant perceptions of the usefulness of the graph as compared to the control (0.084, 95% CI upper bound = 0.700, 95% CI lower bound = -0.533). There was very little difference in the ratings of usefulness for the fan chart ($M = 3.57$, $SD = 1.99$) and the control treatment ($M = 3.67$, $SD = 0.174$). It should be noted that confidence intervals around the effect size encompass zero.

This indicates that presenting uncertainty in the format of a fan chart has a negligible effect on the usefulness of the chart compared to a condition where no uncertainty is presented.

There was a medium effect size for the difference between the fuzzy-fan and fan chart presentations in terms of participant's ratings of the chart's usefulness in informing their day to day job (0.499, 95% CI upper bound = 1.12, 95% CI lower bound = -0.127). The fuzzy-fan chart (M = 2.71, SD = 1.77) was rated more useful than the fan chart (M = 3.57, SD = 1.99).

This indicates that presenting uncertainty in the format of a fuzzy-fan chart makes the chart more useful than when a fan chart format is used, although again, confidence intervals around the effect size encompassed zero.

Q3 How confident would you feel about using Graph A/B/C to inform the work that you do? (7-point scale from 1 (Not confident at all) to 7 (Very confident))

Cohen's d indicated a small effect of the fuzzy fan uncertainty treatment on participant perceptions of how confident they would feel about using the graph to inform their work as compared to the control (-0.375, 95% CI upper bound = 0.239, 95% CI lower bound = -0.989). Ratings of confidence in the use of the fuzzy fan condition were slightly higher (M = 5.24, SD = 1.41) than for the control condition (M = 4.76, SD = 1.55). Note that confidence intervals around this small effect size encompass zero.

This indicates that presenting uncertainty in the format of a fuzzy-fan chart has a negligible effect on experts' feelings of confidence about using that chart to inform their day to day job than using a chart with no uncertainty presented around the central trend.

Cohen’s d indicated a small effect of the fan chart uncertainty treatment on participant confidence as compared to the control (-0.360, 95% CI upper bound = 0.261, 95% CI lower bound = -0.981). There was very little difference in the ratings of confidence in using the fan chart (M = 5.29, SD = 1.59) and confidence in using the control treatment (M = 4.76, SD = 1.55). Again, confidence intervals around this small effect size encompass zero.

This indicates that presenting uncertainty in the format of a fan chart has a negligible effect on participants’ confidence in using that chart to inform their day to day job versus using a chart with no uncertainty presented.

There was a small effect size for the difference between the fuzzy-fan and fan chart presentations in terms of participants’ confidence ratings (0.0087, 95% CI upper bound = 0.625, 95% CI lower bound = -0.607). Ratings of confidence showed little difference between the fuzzy-fan chart (M = 5.24, SD = 1.41) than the fan chart (M = 5.29, SD = 1.59). Again, confidence intervals around this small effect size encompass zero.

This indicates that presenting uncertainty in the format of a fan chart has a negligible effect on participants’ confidence in using that chart to inform their day to day job versus using a fuzzy-fan chart.

Q4 How confident would you feel about using the exact format of Graph A/B/C in a report or article for someone else? (7-point scale from 1 (Not confident at all) to 7 (Very confident))

Cohen's d indicated a small effect of the fuzzy fan uncertainty treatment on participant perceptions of how confident they would feel about using the graph in a report or article for someone else, as compared to using the control graph (-0.428 , 95% CI upper bound = 0.195 , 95% CI lower bound = -1.05). Ratings of confidence in the use of the fuzzy fan condition were slightly higher ($M = 5.05$, $SD = 1.76$) than for the control condition ($M = 4.40$, $SD = 1.54$). Note that confidence intervals around this small effect size encompass zero.

This indicates that presenting uncertainty in the format of a fuzzy-fan chart has a negligible effect on experts' feelings of confidence about using that chart in a report for someone else versus using a chart with no uncertainty presented around the central trend.

Cohen's d indicated a small effect of the fan chart uncertainty treatment on participant confidence as compared to the control (-0.279 , 95% CI upper bound = 0.340 , 95% CI lower bound = -0.898). Ratings of confidence in the use of the fan condition were slightly higher ($M = 5.00$, $SD = 1.65$) than for the control condition ($M = 4.40$, $SD = 1.54$). Note that confidence intervals around this small effect size encompass zero.

This indicates that presenting uncertainty in the format of a fan chart has a negligible effect on experts' feelings of confidence about using that chart in a report for someone else versus using a chart with no uncertainty presented around the central trend.

There was a small effect size for the difference between the fuzzy-fan and fan chart presentations in terms of participants' confidence ratings (-0.137 , 95% CI upper bound = 0.487 , 95% CI lower bound = -0.762). Ratings of confidence were very slightly higher for the fuzzy-fan chart ($M = 5.05$, $SD = 1.76$) than the fan chart ($M = 5.00$, $SD = 1.65$). Again, confidence intervals around the small effect size encompassed zero.

This indicates that presenting uncertainty in the format of a fuzzy-fan chart has a negligible effect on participant's confidence in using that chart in a report for someone else as compared to using a fan chart.

Q5 How easy or difficult do you think people you report to or present to would find Graph A/B/C to understand? (7-point scale from 1 (Very difficult) to 7 (Very easy))

Cohen's d indicated a large effect of the fuzzy fan uncertainty treatment on participant perceptions of ease of others' interpretation as compared to the control (1.06, 95% CI upper bound = 1.71, 95% CI lower bound = 0.411). The fuzzy fan condition was rated less easy for others to understand ($M = 4.19$, $SD = 1.33$) than the control condition ($M = 5.62$, $SD = 1.53$).

This indicates that experts perceive that presenting uncertainty in the format of a fuzzy-fan chart makes the chart less easy for others to understand than when no uncertainty is presented.

Cohen's d indicated a medium effect of the fan chart uncertainty treatment on participant perceptions of ease of others' interpretation as compared to the control (0.701, 95% CI upper bound = 1.34, 95% CI lower bound = 0.066). The fan chart was rated less easy for others to understand ($M = 4.52$, $SD = 1.78$) than the control condition ($M = 5.62$, $SD = 1.53$).

This indicates that experts perceive that presenting uncertainty in the format of a fan chart makes the chart less easy for others to understand than when no uncertainty is presented.

There was a small effect size for the difference between the fuzzy-fan and fan chart presentations in terms of participant perceptions of ease of others' interpretation (0.221, 95% CI upper bound = 0.839, 95% CI lower bound = -0.397). The fuzzy-fan chart ($M = 4.19$, $SD = 1.33$) was rated slightly less easy to understand than the fan chart ($M = 4.52$, $SD = 1.78$). Again, confidence intervals around the small effect size encompassed zero.

This indicates that presenting uncertainty in the format of a fuzzy-fan chart has a negligible effect on perceived ease of others' understanding as compared to using a fan chart.

Qualitative interviews with expert users of migration time series data

Background

The aim of this study was to explore in more detail the effects of communicating uncertainty around trends in migration statistics on expert users of the Migration Statistics Quarterly Report (MSQR). Participants had seen the ‘fuzzy fan’ approach in the latest ONS release, which was the first time that quantified uncertainty had been visualised in the time series. We were keen to gain insights into their reactions to seeing and using this new presentation for the first time as well as understand the context in which the graphics were used.

Summary of sample

Nineteen interviews with expert users of the MSQR were conducted, lasting between 30 and 90 minutes each. These users represented a variety of sectors, including government/civil service, journalists/bloggers, think tanks and academics. Users spanned both ends of the political spectrum and while all would be rated as expert users as compared to a public audience, they had a diversity of expertise with the MSQR and statistics in general.

The MSQR is used for various purposes:

- To produce briefings for MPs and ministers
- To answer specific queries from MPs
- To produce independent briefings for the public
- Think tank press releases issued after each MSQR release to guide journalists’ use and presentation of the new data.
- Newspaper press releases issued after each MSQR release
- To guide other articles by newspapers and think tanks about trends in migration

The MSQR is used alongside various other data sources:

- Home Office visa data
- Exit checks data
- Labour force survey
- Annual population survey
- NiNo data
- Census data
- Eurostat data
- UN data
- Statistics authorities of other countries

Sections of the MSQR that are used most frequently:

Section	Number of people (Total N = 24)	Comments	Example quote
Headline figures	17	Users mentioned that bullet points at the top of the report were useful as an overall summary	"When we do the initial "what's in this report that I need to know", the first thing we would do would be to look at the bullets."
Raw data	15		"We'd look for... any new information about the statistics that we didn't know before, and then having checked that we'd go straight to the data tables and update all of our charts and written analysis based on what we'd found in the data tables."
Tables in the report	15		
Statistician's comments	11	Users felt these comments gave good direction/guidance over what they could and couldn't say based on the release. Some users wished for even more guidance	"The statistician's comment is extremely useful in so far as it basically tells you what you can say. I've found in the past and with a lot of other statistical releases still that it's somehow a little difficult to work out how exactly to parse the bullet points into the headlines which you can say without falling foul of reporting them inaccurately or misleadingly. The statistician's comment is very helpful because it basically gives a very curated commentary of the latest figures so that's very useful."
Graphs (charts)	8		"[The graphs] give us an immediate picture, and if there's a significant change then that is worthy of note." "Looking at the graph would tend to be just to get an instant instinctive broad picture of what's happened, but the graph... wouldn't instinctively communicate whether the change was statistically significant or really what the headline change was."
Text of the report	8	Some users commented that they skim the main body of the report to identify specific analyses conducted and methodological changes since the previous release	
Things you need to know section	7		"So I always start with the bullet points and then go on to the things you need to know about this release section and the statistician's comments. I find the things that you need to know about the release section mainly helps with background and helping me know where I need to click next after I'm done with this report, as I say there are other figures and releases which you may want to look at and stuff."

General comment on this report

The report is structured where possible into clear themes that emerged from the interviews. These included both positive and negative feedback about the graphical presentation of uncertainty, critiques of the underlying data, a wish for greater guidance on how to use the report, and a desire for better communication about data adjustments, methodological changes and future development plans. Direct, anonymised quotes from users are included in many sections to support each summary and sub-point made as context/data to evidence the themes that were identified during the interview and analysis process.

In our quantitative survey of expert users above, there was the opportunity for participants to add qualitative comments on the different charts they saw (the control chart, the fuzzy fan and the fan chart). These additional comments are integrated into the themes of the present report where appropriate.

Themes

Positive feedback:

Users were positive and acknowledging of the fact that the ONS are making effort to improve the quality and presentation of their migration statistics. There was also appreciation for the fact that the job of collating and communicating this data is not easy.

"I'll make the general comment that I think the team and the people at the ONS who work on the MSQR are really great because you see constant kind of innovation in these releases that's really pleasing to see."

"[For] people who work on the MSQR... it can feel very difficult to make a statistical release because everyone has different demands as to what they want from it. Some people want this, that. They want it in a different order, they want it in a different priority. So I completely respect that they have a thankless task in putting this all in."

General positives about recent changes to the MSQR:

Users were appreciative of some of the changes made to recent editions of the MSQR e.g. the presentation of uncertainty in the graphs; adjustments to student immigration figures and other data; increased emphasis on the statistician's comment.

"I actually welcome the fact that the ONS have adjusted [the student migration data], I'd like to see that adjustment make its way into the [data] table somehow, because I think if you know there are problems with the data you need to own up to them."

"I was really pleased when I saw that ONS had started saying actually our best estimate is not the IPS figure here, we're going to adjust it using the visa data to say something else."

"The statistician's comment is very helpful because it basically gives a very curated commentary of the latest figures so that's very useful."

**Positive feedback about presentation of uncertainty in graphs:
Several users had positive comments about the graphical presentation of uncertainty around trends in the migration data.**

There was suggestion that presenting uncertainty avoids accusations that the figures are too black and white, and that over time, presenting uncertainty should help people gain a more nuanced view of migration trends. Some users did highlight the value of having a central trend line to represent the “big picture” however.

Others found the uncertainty a useful resource to refer to when trying to correct misinterpretations from various individuals (e.g. journalists, MPs etc). It was also noted that presenting uncertainty is valuable as it may allow for more informed conclusions to be drawn by some users, and is more honest.

- *“This type of chart with uncertainty ranges helps illustrate that estimates are just that - indications of approximate scale, and not absolute values.”*
- *“I think it’s good in general, I think they should definitely keep doing it.”*
- *“I really like it, it’s a visual reminder of the uncertainty of the figures involved”*
- *“I think there would be some variation across readers, but those who take the time to look at it will come to a more informed conclusion.”*
- *“It may be harder for others to understand but it is more honest and that is what matters”*

When asked for their opinions on a simple line chart where no uncertainty was presented, several users said that it was easy to understand but expressed concern that it would be easy to misinterpret and to mistakenly assume a level of certainty in the central trend line that is not there.

- *“Easy to understand but also easy to misinterpret given there's no indication of confidence intervals”*
- *“I think [people] might misinterpret it as the one and only truth. They might not be aware of the caveats.”*
- *“Easy to interpret but does not recognise the limitations of sample survey data (and wider uncertainties about IPS processes)”*
- *“I think non-technical readers of a report would find the graph easy to interpret. However, they might skip over the health warnings that this is an estimate, so I would feel uneasy about how they interpret it.”*

- *“Easy to understand but conveys a certainty in the data which is not true of the data.”*

Concerns about presentation of uncertainty in graphs:

Several users had concerns about the graphical presentation of uncertainty around trends in the migration data.

There were a variety of concerns regarding the possibility that graphical presentation of uncertainty may lead to misinterpretation of the data:

- **Uncertainty may detract from the clarity of the general long-term trend:** *“[People]... don’t tend to [go to a graph] to find specific figures, they do it to look at it and to draw a general story about the trends. They maybe take a particular interest in what the latest changes are up or down but generally speaking you look at a graph and you just see a shape, and that tends to be probably what you’d retain if anything... adding too much visual faff to that might just make it more confusing to take that very general story. I think uncertainty probably becomes more important when you look at the more recent figures... but it seems a little less important when you’re talking about the shape of a long-term trend.”*
- **Presentation of uncertainty may make people less likely to believe clear, long-term trends:** *“If you throw too many caveats at it, it might make people unwilling to even believe the shape is true when of course the shape is overwhelmingly likely to be true, or the broad picture is overwhelmingly likely to be accurate, so uncertainty can have the opposite effect, it can overly distort the fact that something is actually probably ok in the grand scheme of things.”*
- **Presentation of uncertainty may drive people to use other, less reliable datasets:** *“You don’t want to give too much uncertainty to your headline figures so that people don’t use them... People [may] use even less reliable data than what we’ve got already.”*
- **Presenting uncertainty may provide more opportunity for misinterpretation of the data, with people focusing on those numbers across the range of uncertainty that fit best with their prior beliefs. It may also enhance the possibility for deliberate misinterpretation, allowing a particular desired narrative to be presented and evidenced.**
- **Presentation of revised and unrevised estimates on the same time series without clear labelling is misleading, as these two types of estimates are governed by different conditions:** *“The other element is the fact that some of the figures are revised and other aren’t, and that’s good I think it’s a good visual way of showing that those figures are different in form to the most recent net migration figures, that said it doesn’t really equip me to know exactly what to do with them.”*

There was also concern expressed about how presenting statistical uncertainty without any reference to other, unquantified uncertainties could be damaging, as it mistakenly implies that the data are 100% reliable provided the confidence intervals are taken into account during interpretation and presentation of the data.

- *“My residual concern is that, by itself, the visual representation of statistical uncertainty in the charts could promote false confidence in the migration estimates, because this is not the only kind of uncertainty surrounding them. To be clear: I don't think this is a reason not to show the statistical uncertainty, but I think the other types of uncertainty affecting the data must also somehow be communicated to the user.”*
- *“Be more forward about the unknown sources of uncertainty.”*
- *“Users think that as long as they take into account confidence intervals, they're ok.”*
- *“Caveats being made available in the figures would be useful. Making it clear if quality/reliability is low.”*
- *“The whole story isn't being given in the data, it ignores all the things that aren't measured. So one issue is how these things are being counted and also how they are assigned a level of usefulness that might not be reflected in reality.”*

On a practical level, the scale of the graph may be too small for the uncertainty information represented by the fuzziness to be properly interpreted. Thus it is possible that the graphs are not conveying the information desired.

- *“When the estimate itself is quite big, the confidence interval is usually comparatively quite small in scale, so the fuzziness is quite dense, and sometimes it's quite hard to actually see whether there's any change in size of the confidence intervals over time... It's quite hard to quantify how big the confidence interval is.”*

The value of presenting uncertainty around more granular data (e.g. that for different local authorities) was also questioned, with concerns that confidence intervals are so large at this level it may not even be possible to make inferences about what is going on.

- *“When we start getting down into those datasets you'll often find that the numbers get pretty small and the estimates pretty small... and often because sample size is really small the confidence interval is basically as big as the estimate itself, or maybe even bigger. [For example in] the local migration indicators data... there'll be estimates of how many foreign nationals are living in a particular area and like let's say it's 5000 and then the confidence interval +/- 7000... they're so woolly, that you can't really be sure that there are even any*

foreign nationals at all, because it's 5000 give or take 7000. So, when zero falls within the confidence interval it's not really clear what to do with that... The ONS actually says in its notes... that if the confidence interval is higher than the estimate itself then they caution against even using the estimate, which makes me wonder why they bother publishing it, because it's too tempting to not use it... I don't really know what the solution to it is. I wouldn't necessarily like to see the ONS get rid of those estimates, because then we wouldn't have any idea, and it's good to at least know perhaps a range... maybe that would be quite a nice halfway point... for areas where the confidence interval is as big as the estimate itself to just have some kind of ranges for them to estimate... Rather than to say oh we estimate that it's 5000 give or take 5000 each way, maybe [say] we think there are 0 to 10,000 migrants in this area or in this category..."

Some users commented that the way the uncertainty is displayed could be seen as just colourful decoration to draw attention to the chart, rather than being understood as actual information in itself, and made suggestions for possible improvements.

- *"The fuzziness makes looking at the graph a bit less pleasant an experience. I would expect people might instinctively assume it is unhelpful funky decoration than a serious attempt to communicate uncertainty."*
- *"Adding visual elements can be misconstrued as decoration when actually you're trying to make a serious point. So I think that's a danger to be, to be aware of and to be considerate of."*
- *"Maybe the simplest way to [communicate uncertainty would be] to make use of images that are already familiar to the public that communicate caution or uncertainty like, you know, the yellow triangle with an exclamation mark, or something, just something that instantly appeals to a sense of caution rather than necessarily a visual inflection that people almost have to learn your visual vocabulary before they can get anything out of what you're producing."*

Some users were indifferent about the presentation of uncertainty graphically:

- *"We are used to working with data, so having the uncertainty presented in [the charts] is fine, but we don't mind if it's there in the visual or if we have to dig into the dataset to get the uncertainty [ourselves]."*

Some users wished for uncertainty to be discussed more explicitly in the text of the report:

- *"ONS could improve their commentary when publishing this sort of [uncertainty] chart - as they still tend to discuss the central estimates only."*

Labelling the uncertainty presented in the graphs as "known uncertainty" (via the legend) was thought by some to be useful as it implies the existence of unknown uncertainties too, however others were concerned that this quantified uncertainty is still an estimate,

not a known quantity, and thus that the phrase “known uncertainty” may be misleading and/or confusing. There was also concern that the average user might not understand what the phrase “known uncertainty” actually means and thus that this phrase needs defining.

- *“In the newer editions, known uncertainty is labelled as such – this is useful as it implies unknown uncertainty is there too.”*
- *“Most of the people I present statistics to would not understand 'known uncertainty'.”*
- *“There is no such thing as "known uncertainty" as opposed to 95% confidence intervals or standard deviations.”*
- *“The phrase 'known uncertainty in survey estimate' is unhelpful. The uncertainty is as much an estimate, if not more so, than the central survey estimate - and is not really a known quantity. This adds confusion rather than clarity I feel.”*

Some users expressed concerns about the fact that it was not made explicit that three quarters of the data for each point on the graph are overlapping with the data from the previous quarter. They requested that this was better communicated to users:

- *“The uncertainty is in relation to changes between different points in time, but there is no indication in this chart that the estimates are based on overlapping time periods (four rolling quarters) rather than (as with the LFS stock estimates say) a snapshot at a single point in time. This feels more important to me, to get across to the reader, than the issues around confidence intervals.”*

When asked about a fuzzy-fan and a fan-chart presentation of the migration data specifically, users thought that the different confidence intervals (30, 60, 95%) needed to be defined, and that guidance on how to interpret these different intervals, particularly in terms of significance, needed to be provided.

- *“As a statistician I can infer that the boundaries to the main estimate are different confidence intervals - perhaps 50%, 65% and 95%. But to a non-expert it is not clear at all what the difference is between these lines and which one they should be looking at. There is also no real benefit to knowing that a change is statistically significant based on a 50% or 65% confidence interval. This would not be considered a meaningful increase in the social sciences. And if that would not be considered a meaningful increase then someone using this data may as well just use changes in the main estimate...I've mainly been thinking here about the use of these charts to assess whether change over time is significant. Since people are often looking for a 'story' when they examine data like this, the tendency is to try to make comparisons between different things (points in time, lines on the chart). Of course, there are other uses of the charts where the gradient approach [fuzzy-fan] is also effective - e.g. if the main purpose of the chart is to simply*

show the level of net migration over a short space of time and to convey uncertainty around the estimate.”

- *“Without saying what the bands represent this is pretty useless.”*
- *“The points in the shading are easy for statisticians to understand but not the general reader I feel.”*

When comparing the Fan chart and the Fuzzy-fan chart, users had mixed opinions on preference between the two. Note that our quantitative analyses with a public audience showed very little difference in the effects of these two presentation types on perceptions of uncertainty, trustworthiness, reliability and accuracy, although there was a slight preference in some analyses for the fuzzy-fan:

- *“Personally, I think that the [Fan chart] rather than the [Fuzzy-Fan chart] could be more useful in describing uncertainty, if provided with a key to explain e.g. this colour represents 90% certainty that the true figure lies in this range; next colour 95%, etc.”*
- *“The fan chart is less intuitive than the fuzzy chart because the clear lines encourage one to think too much about what the lines mean (i.e. what % confidence interval is being represented where), which is not really the point of the graph.”*
- *“[The fan chart is] superior to [the fuzzy fan], it seems, as it's nicer on the eye and clearer to see the boundaries. I expect this is a slight compromise on the precision of the graphic as confidence intervals don't suddenly stop, they tail off exponentially. But definitely a worthwhile compromise as who will care about this minor detail.”*
- *“The lack of gradation [in the fan chart] implies there are more distinct categories of likelihood [than in the fuzzy-fan chart].”*
- *“The visual representation of uncertainty is on the whole an improvement on the chart showing just a plain line. And I think (but am not sure) that the simpler binned uncertainty levels [the fan chart] are perhaps easier to read than the incremental gradient [the fuzzy-fan chart].”*

Concerns about the underlying data:

Several users expressed concerns about aspects of the underlying data and revisions to it, as well as the way in which this information is communicated.

It was considered potentially misleading that both the census adjusted and more recent, unadjusted figures are presented on the same graph without clear acknowledgement that different conditions govern these different types of data:

- *“Any of the estimates that come after the 2011 census are governed by the one set of conditions; they are primarily survey based... It may be that we need to draw a line or shade that whole area of the chart to indicate that [the pre-2011 census revised estimates represent] a different measurement period governed by different conditions.”*
- *“At the moment, before the [post-2011] survey-based estimates with the margin of error, net migration is just represented with a solid line [however the pre-2011 net migration figures have] some uncertainty, because they’re adjustments that the ONS has made based on other sources. It’s a kind of unquantifiable uncertainty but there is still some uncertainty. [Representing the pre-2011 net migration trend with no uncertainty] sort of implies that the same conditions apply but the margin of error has disappeared, whereas I would argue that [the pre and post-2011 figures] are qualitatively different numbers and that should be reflected somehow.”*

Some users thought it was misleading and potentially confusing that not all of the figures in the census-adjusted period are actually adjusted. Users still use the historical time series so would like to be able to compare effectively and reliably.

- *“In the period where the revisions apply, net migration was revised but immigration and emigration weren’t revised. ONS said they didn’t know by how much immigration and emigration should be revised because the error in the headline net figure might be due to more immigration or less emigration and they couldn’t be sure which it was... I think that that decision is a mistake as what essentially ONS is saying is that rather than give you adjusted figures which might be wrong, we’d rather give you unadjusted figures which definitely are wrong... [In turn] you shouldn’t put confidence intervals around the [pre-2011] immigration and emigration lines because it implies that the figure is probably somewhere in that range when in practice we know that both of those figures are probably wrong, definitely the immigration figure, we know for certain that the immigration figure is too low because it hasn’t been adjusted, and we know that underestimation of immigration was the main problem.”*
- *“A lot of the old data is revised and it’s not comprehensively revised – so some figures like the net migration series have been revised but the inflow and outflow figures haven’t. So there’s still a great deal of uncertainty about what actually happened in the mid 2000s. There’s basically a sense that the immigration figures are too low. And yet they haven’t been revised. So we basically know that some of those old figures are wrong, and we have a good idea which direction they’re wrong in, but we don’t have all the alternatives. We’ve got some revised figures and not others.”*
- *“I’d really like them to come up with a revised series for all of the components of migration for the census period and to... publish an estimate of what they think student net migration is based on the exit checks data, because those are the questions that people want answered.”*

- *“When some of the figures have been revised, that alone doesn’t give me information... to know what to do with them. It doesn’t tell me whether I should use them with a footnote, or use them with an immediate by the way this has been revised, or avoid using them, or just put some massive exclamation mark on them saying they’re uncertain.”*

There was some concern that other data on migration doesn’t match up with the IPS data:

- *“NiNos and visa statistics don’t necessarily cohere entirely with what the IPS is telling us, so there’s an element of uncertainty. Is there something systematic about this survey that’s under or overcounting some of the things it’s trying to count?”*

There was concern about inconsistent labelling across the data e.g. “emigration by former immigrants whose main reason for migration was formal study” is labelled as experimental, but other subgroups in the same section and the total column (of which the experimental statistics are part) are not labelled as experimental:

- *“I think there is an issue with the way that data is presented in the release, because if you go and look at that Table 4 in the MSQR and you look for emigration by former immigrants whose main reason for migration was formal study, you’ll notice that it says experimental statistics... The problem is that they don’t say that any of the other categories are experimental, and they don’t say that the total is experimental. If that formal study figure is wrong, then it is either the case that the total is wrong, or it is the case that one of the other categories at least is wrong as well, so they should either all be labelled experimental, or both former immigrants and the total should be labelled as experimental. That’s slightly by the by but my point is that I think the way it’s presented in the spreadsheet underplays the significance of the problems that you’ve got around that data.”*

It was highlighted as problematic that data adjustments made in specific MSQR reports don’t always get applied to the underlying raw data table e.g. the recent adjustment for the undercount of student immigration. In a few quarters’ time, people won’t be looking at a particular chart in the August 2018 release specifically for the data in that year, they’ll be looking at the raw data table. Thus, if the adjustment featured in the August 2018 release is not included in the underlying raw data table, it will simply be forgotten as time goes on.

- *“I think the only place you can get that adjustment is if you go to the bulletin itself on the web browser and then download the underlying data to the charts... So, it’s kind of strongly encouraging you just to use the original estimates, the unadjusted estimates, but then using those you’ll come to different conclusions probably than the ONS. You know so, your best estimate will be something else. So, yeah, I think it’s probably just likely to confuse people to be honest, if they’re coming to different conclusions than the ONS is writing then they probably*

assume they're doing something wrong and probably just give up on the whole thing. And it's easy to forget that the adjustment's even there. In the notes that accompany the data tables, I can picture if they don't adopt this as a formal adjustment, and maybe they'll stop doing this dotted line in the bulletin, in a few quarters time everyone will have just forgotten about that."

It was also mentioned that the issues underlying the IPS and subsequent data adjustments need to be made clear to users upfront in the report:

- *"The big challenge with the IPS is that it underestimated net migration in the decades to 2011, its measure of student emigration has never been robust and it took us several years to find that out, and we've just discovered that its student immigration numbers were wrong for a period of at least a year. How do you quantify that kind of nagging doubt about the fundamental quality of the survey and what it's trying to measure in a statistical way? I don't know. I mean, that's a really hard question and I don't know, but there needs to be some way of, I just think that the statistics deserve way more of a health warning than they get. Because the trouble is, if you don't know this stuff, if you don't know the long and complicated backstory to the IPS and its history and its methods, it's actually very hard to interpret the data in these tables correctly. If you don't know this stuff the tables are a minefield of potential misinterpretation... You need to make people aware somehow of that kind of anxiety about the IPS as a data source."*

A wish for greater guidance and better communication:

Many users expressed a wish for greater guidance over how to use the information in the report, especially regarding how to understand and use revised vs unrevised figures, how to understand and use information on uncertainty, and how to understand and use significant and non-significant data. There was also a wish from some for greater comment on how recent trends fit within the historical time-series.

Users said it was difficult to know how to use data where some figures are revised and some are not:

- *"Some of the figures are revised and other aren't... and this is actually something, it comes across in a lot of different statistics that we have to handle... when you get data over time that has essentially got some kind of comparability issue, in this case that some of the figures have been revised and others haven't... What do you want me to do with that? Does that mean I should or shouldn't use this? ...Should I use it uncritically, or must I mention that the old figure has been revised whereas the new figure hasn't? It's a theme that comes up in a lot of things when you have incomparable or uncertain time series, it's actually equipping someone to know what to do with the fact that it's not comparable, whether that means you can or can't use it."*

There was some confusion over how to understand the uncertainty presented in the charts and around the data, and how to understand and report significant vs non-significant changes:

- *“[When] trying to report the numbers, we’ve grappled with whether we can report a change basically straightforwardly, or with some degree of uncertainty. So, for instance if the headline net migration changes by 30,000, should we just report migration is up, or should we report “estimated” migration is up, or should we just report migration hasn’t significantly changed? So... if a change is say within the margin of error, not statistically significant, that presents a slight dilemma because obviously the estimate is pointing up, but it’s not statistically significant, so you end up thinking so how exactly is the right way to report that? Now the releases tend not to spoon feed you too much in that, they tend to say like this has happened and then the second line is but by the way it’s not statistically significant, so the kind of dilemmas that you face are should I report basically what they’ve said, that it looks like it’s up but that’s not significant? Or should I start by saying we don’t know what’s happened because it changed within the margin of error?”*
- *“The extra difficulty that presents for us is the fact that statistical significance is presented in quite a binary form. It either is or it isn’t. It either falls within this margin or it doesn’t. And a difficulty we’ve had a few times in the past is that, if a change is very close to being statistically significant but isn’t, it nevertheless holds that it’s very likely to have changed, it just doesn’t happen to have met the threshold for significance, and I think, it’s very, it’s very awkward to try and communicate that because if something’s say 94% likely to have changed, that falls below the threshold statistical significance, but it’s still overwhelmingly likely to be a genuine change, so it seems like a reporter still needs to say well that this has probably changed, probably net migration probably has gone up or probably has gone down, but yet the manner of communication, the language of communication of the releases is quite binary and so can be quite difficult to interpret what the ONS actually wants [us] to be saying. Obviously the ONS shouldn’t be directing [us] exactly what to say but I’m all for being spoon fed recommendations on what to say! That helps a lot... To couch that previous point in a specific example [that] might have happened in the February release or the last release from last year, but it was I think that there was a fairly large drop in net migration or it might have been EU net migration and the drop actually didn’t fall within, it wasn’t big enough to be a statistically significant drop, however it was very close to being that, so a lot of newspapers went and reported oh yes it’s dropped and without much caveat. And our initial line was going to be wow, wow hang on this isn’t statistically significant, but then we kind of rowed back from that because we kind of thought well yes, but it’s still very close to being significant so it seems like the top line should still be this has probably happened rather than the top line being it’s not significant whether it’s changed in any way. So that’s the tension I’m kind of drawing out there.”*

There was some confusion over about how to handle/report data for which confidence intervals encapsulate zero:

- *“When zero falls within the confidence interval it’s not really clear what to do with that...”*

Some users wanted guidance on how to report the trustworthiness of the MSQR data:

- *“I find it really difficult, well we all do, when we report on migration figures, what’s our top line as to can you fundamentally trust this source? Like is it fundamentally robust?... In an MSQR, when you go to it, it doesn’t really spoon feed you with what’s the latest, what’s the ONS’ latest view on what you should say. Does the ONS want you to reference this wider debate? Does the ONS still stand by its own figures or would it prefer you to emphasise that they’re estimates and that there’s work ongoing? So, in the MSQR and those old reports, I’d still like more explicit advice and guidance on what you can say, what you can’t say, what we’d like you to say. And my job... is obviously to interpret whether I should just copy what you’re saying! But I think it’s the statisticians’ job to guide us as much as they can on those big questions.”*

Some users wanted more commentary and guidance on how the most recent trends in migration fit within the broader, historical picture:

- *“What I’d like to see and what I think would be very helpful is for migration releases to have this kind of continuous reporting of the historical picture. So the bullet points rightly at the top focus on the latest changes, but I also think there are theoretical bullet points you could have in every release that constantly comment on the historical picture, so constantly say so we don’t actually know what happened to migration exactly between 2001 and 2011 because there was this revision therefore when you report on this we recommend that you do x, y or z. And I think that kind of just continuous big picture would actually serve the debate just as much as the focus on all the latest changes.”*

Other concerns:

Some users had concerns over the quarterly nature of the release and how it may misleadingly imply an important change has occurred since the last quarter, thus creating a necessity for comment. The politicised nature of migration statistics was also highlighted:

- *“The quarterly nature of the release implies that, every time there is a new release, a change must have occurred that needs to be reported on. Each new release also implies a degree of certainty about the data being presented. People think, if the government is telling us about this, it must be important!”*

- *“So whenever the next stats are out later in November there’ll be an expectation from my news editors to be on standby at 9.30 in the morning on that particular day to crash through the report as quickly as possible to get some headlines out about this that and the other, and that ultimately comes down to what’s up and what’s down because of the... political context within which migration statistics are consumed, because you know, it’s the state of policy objectives of the government. So it’s not kind of, you know while the figures themselves are effectively like a raw data set in some respects, you know you’ve got this great big political thing on the side which is informing how we use them as well, which makes it quite difficult.”*
- *“I think the concept of statistical releases is probably a little unusual to a lot of people. I think a lot of people, maybe we’re in a time when people expect to be able to go to a web page, a consistent webpage that they can bookmark and find what the truth is, what the facts are. You know, like you go to the Wikipedia page and it will tell you something about, that’s I think how a lot of people operate. And it’s how I’d like to operate. So rather than going to the latest report, if essentially things are on some kind of live page where you instantly get this is the current picture, this is the big historical picture, and have that updated as new analysis and new data and new commentary comes in from the statisticians, that serves me as a user extraordinarily well, and I think is probably the direction that a lot of these statistical releases have to go in in the future.”*

Some concerns were expressed about the use of language in the reports:

- *“Our particular interest in this is the selectivity of the data and how it’s presented. We’re concerned with how it’s packaged in certain ways.”*
- *“They used to use words like increased/decreased even if a change was not statistically significant, but I think they have changed this now, so this is better, as before it was implying that the increase wasn’t actually an increase, which no one understood.”*

Concerns already addressed:

Desire was expressed for greater transparency over the discrepancies between the IPS estimates and other data sources e.g. Home Office exit checks data, the Labour Force survey.

- *This has already been implemented via Figures 5, 6 and 7 in the August 2018 release and Figures 5 and 6 in the November 2018 release.*

There was frustration over the fact that tables in the report show year to year changes but then captions state not to compare year to year.

- *This year to year comparison has been removed from tables in the November 2018 report.*

Other general requests:

Some users wished for a single, rolling document detailing all data and all methodological changes in their most up to date state in one place:

- *“ONS have a number of different reports that they update at different times, which is challenging, as updates will be released to different documents at different times so it is difficult to understand what the state of affairs is at any one point in time.”*
- *“If there was some kind of central repository or just a static page I knew where I could find the latest that would be great... I’m not always confident as to whether the latest developments in how the statistics are being gathered and analysed has rendered any of that commentary obsolete. Because I know that the ONS are doing work with their student migration estimates, it sometimes gives me pause for thought whether that means that we need to change some of our lines that we base on those various documents.... When things change and we know that it’s a changing picture in how migration statistics are gathered and communicated, all that guidance needs to be dynamic and it needs to be constantly keeping up wherever it exists, or at least wherever the ONS intends for it to be reused. So that’s what just creates a little difficulty, because it’s a changing picture you can’t always rely on the bookmarks you have on your internet tabs, essentially!”*
- *“I and my colleagues have read all the accessory documents [to the main MSQR report], however the vast majority of people would not know they were there and not understand them even if they did. So the emphasis has to be on communicating the uncertainty and the quality issues upfront in the report.”*
- *“It would be really, really great to think about whether the richness that comes in ad hoc statistical releases could be transferred to a go-to dynamic point [a live page] where people are constantly getting the latest and the best information about what the figures are, how to use them, how not to use them, and what the context is [including historical data].”*

Some users wished for greater communication on the direction and progress of future developments, including the use of admin data, and in turn what the impact of these changes would be on the past and present data series:

- *“It’s very easy to lose track as to where the ONS is in the process of its internal improvement of its own estimates, and the work it’s doing on improving its student estimates for instance.”*
- *“What are the impacts of the methodological changes on the series?... Because clearly there’s going to be some quite significant changes over the coming years*

with their development program...ONS [need to] really try and say in advance what impact [the development changes are] gonna make on the new series and what changes they're going to make in the next release..."

Some users wanted more data and less description in the release, but others liked the descriptive commentary:

- *"It's not the visuals themselves that is our main concern, but the communication and selection of the data, what is being emphasised, what is being ignored. Not the data capture, but the data packaging which is the concern... If [the ONS] were less descriptive and just showed more data, that would help, that would be more useful. Show people the nuances, make that easily accessible and obvious.... The key thing is, the people looking at this whether journalists, statisticians whatever, they're all people who need to know what's going on, you don't need to worry about overloading them with information, the quarterly reports can provide more detail, a more nuanced picture. The audience is not the man on the street. So not being fearful of giving a more detailed granular level of the data is important."*
- *"[I like the] richness of commentary and analysis and context that a statistical release is so great at doing"*

Some users requested that ONS take greater ownership over providing a "best estimate" for different components of migration using the different datasets available (IPS, NiNo, Exit Checks etc):

- *"I'd like ONS to take more ownership of the responsibility of deciding what our best estimate of migration, any given component of migration, is over the last twenty years. Even if it has to be a different dataset, even if you continue to publish the survey-based estimates separately so that people can see them."*
- *"If ONS had a best estimate for immigration and emigration within each category, for any given cell in the tables that are in the MSQR, if you had a best estimate, then I think it would make the visualisation job much easier... Where the best estimate is an adjusted figure [you use] a dotted line without a confidence interval and explain non-statistical uncertainty applies, and where the best estimate is a survey-based estimate show it as a solid line with a confidence interval."*

Development of Open Source software to produce the different visualisations of uncertainty

Background

Currently there are no publicly available tools to easily generate timeseries with uncertainty. In order to allow communicators to create visualisations of uncertainty we created a library in python, using plotly graphics to create the four chart types we had user-tested in our experiments.

The solid *fan chart* plots time series values with uniformly coloured 30%, 60% and 95% confidence bands.

In the *density (fuzzy) chart*, n colour bands are calculated from given 95% confidence bands assuming a normal distribution.

In the standard *error bar* chart a uniform colour paints the given confidence band.

The *fuzzy fan chart* derives from the solid fan chart but blurs the band boundaries. The blur does not derive from the data series but is created to form the illusion of fuzziness.

Library Features

- Customisable colour for uncertainty
- Any of standard plotly customization such as labels, fonts, tickets, margin etc can be used
- Chart data can be exported and added to other plotly charts and in any of other plotly compatible languages such as R, MATLAB
- Plotly chart can be added on top of uncertainty chart.
- Compatible with jupyter notebook.
- Export as html for embedding on a website.

Technologies used

- We used Python as it is a popular language for data science and machine learning. (see ref 1)
- Plotly is a popular open source charting library which provides interface with multiple languages such as Javascript, Python, R, MATLAB etc. It also provides online interface to edit the chart as shown below.
- This choice of technology means that these plots may be embedded in jupyter notebooks.

Implementation Details

The [Plotly](#) toolset provides a very useful graphics environment with an editing interface for graph annotations and interfaces to many languages, including python.

Plotly uses SVG (Structured Vector Graphics) to generate graph glyphs but does not provide an interface to SVG filters. We must therefore use polygons of different colours to depict the uncertainty bands. The density charts and the fuzzy fan charts use many thin polygons to achieve the necessary gradients.

Colour choices for uncertainty chart are based on confidence intervals of standard distribution translated as opacity value of rgba.

Challenges

Creating the fuzzy fan chart presented interesting challenges. We discovered that it often illustrates a visual artefact whereby colour boundaries are perceived when no such boundary exists. We tried different easing function to change colour profile and this seems to help in some cases.

Below are examples of fuzzy plot with different colour profile.

Linear gradient

With cube tweening function

Depending on colours used and how zoomed in fuzziness and artifact changes.

Possible future work

Mapping probability densities to colour is not straightforward. It is influenced by non-linearities in visual perception and differences due to display parameters such as brightness, contrast, and gamma. We have investigated some of these issues using a different online fan-plotter tool published at <https://wintoncentre.maths.cam.ac.uk/fanplotter>. It is possible that integrating a well behaved colour scale into the library – we suggest the cube-helix scale – will allow the user to generate good looking output easier.

GitHub: <https://github.com/WintonCentre/python-fuzzy-plots>

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